

Continued from the paper of *The Dark Side of Rich Rewards: Understanding and Mitigating Noise in VLM Rewards*, the technical appendix consists of the following:

- **§A Detailed Problem Setting**, which provides a detailed problem setting of the instruction-following reinforcement learning. This is referred to in Section III and Section IV.
- **§B Theoretical Analysis and Proofs**, which is referred to in Section IV
- **§C Additional Notes on Theoretical Setting**
- **§D Implementation Details of the Experiments**, which specify the implementation details for both the first and second stage experiments in Section V-A and Section VII respectively.
- **§E Additional Details of the Experiments of False Positive Rewards**, which is referred in Section V-A.
- **§F Details of Showing the Prevalence of False Positives in VLM Cosine Similarity Scores**, which provides extra figures that cannot be in the main body due to page limit.
- **§G Impact of Reward Model Quality on Policy Learning Efficiency: Supplementary Experiments and Quantitative Analysis in Montezuma**, which provides extra evaluation results to further illustrate false positive rewards hinders agent learning.
- **§H Pseudo-code for Empirical Quantile Calculation for Binary Signal Threshold**, which is referred in Section VI-A.
- **§I Additional Implementation Details of the Experiments of BiMI Reward Function**, which is referred in Section VII.
- **§J Detailed Experiment Results of BiMI Reward Function**, which provides detailed experiment results of BiMI reward function, which is referred in Section VII.
- **§K Deprecated Convergence Analysis**, It is retained here solely for reference and backtracking purposes. As the more rigorous theoretical analysis is constructed, the content of this section is now **deprecated**.

A. Detailed Problem Setting

1) *The Pointer Mechanism in Reward Machine*: In our problem setting, $r^v(\tau_t, l_{m(t)})$ is the VLM based reward at time step t evaluated using the sub-trajectory τ_t is the sub-trajectory up to time t .

Existing VLM-reward implementations applied a pointer mechanism that decide which instruction should the agent consider at the current step. We follow this implementation and denote the pointer as $m(t)$. It indicates the current instruction of the agent is trying to complete at time step t . $m(t)$ is updated according to the following rule:

$$m(t+1) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } t = 0 \\ m(t) + 1 & \text{if instr. } l_{m(t)} \text{ completed at } t \\ m(t) & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

In both the ELLM and the Pixl2R framework that uses VLM-based rewards, the assessment of whether instruction $l_{m(t)}$ is completed at time t is based on the cumulative reward for that instruction. The pointer remains on the current instruction until the accumulated reward reaches a predetermined threshold. For a detailed pseudo-code of the existing VLM reward + RL algorithm, please refer to Appendix D2. Note that our proposed BiMI reward function uses a different mechanism to determine if instruction $l_{m(t)}$ is completed at time t .

In logic, **an atomic sentence** is a type of statement which cannot be broken down into other simpler sentences. While the pointer mechanism effectively enforces the sequential ordering of instructions at a higher level, each individual instruction within the expert walkthrough is not necessarily **atomic**. This means that a single instruction can encapsulate multiple finer-grained requirements for the agent’s behavior. Therefore, even though the pointer mechanism is implemented, the internal composition of each instruction is not strictly enforced. Consequently, the issue of “composition insensitivity” can arise when the VLM tries to align agents’ trajectories with non-atomic instruction sentences.

Just as potential-based reward shaping (PBRS) modifies the original MDP into a reshaped MDP through the use of auxiliary rewards, the HuRL framework similarly transforms the original MDP \mathcal{M} into a new MDP $\tilde{\mathcal{M}} = \langle \mathcal{S}, \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{P}, s_0, \tilde{r}, \tilde{\gamma} \rangle$, employing a heuristic-based auxiliary reward h , along with a coefficient $\beta \in [0, 1]$ that scales the auxiliary rewards. Thus, the updated reward function can be written as:

$$\tilde{r}(s, a) = r^e(s, a, s') + (1 - \beta)\gamma \mathbb{E}_{s' \sim \mathcal{P}(\cdot | s, a)}[h(s')] \quad \text{and} \quad \tilde{\gamma} = \beta\gamma$$

We also provide the formal definition of false negative reward as below.

Definition A.1 (False Negative Rewards). A false negative reward occurs when:

Instruction-Following Perspective: The VLM-based reward $r^v(\tau_t, l_{m(t)}) \approx 0$ for a trajectory τ_t that *does* satisfy instruction $l_{m(t)}$.

Heuristic Perspective: The heuristic $h(s_t) \approx 0 < V^*(s_t)$, underestimating the optimal value of s_t .

2) *Detailed Terminology*: This section contains detailed terminology from both the standard RL and the HuRL framework.

We start by setting clear the terminology. The original MDP is defined by a tuple $\langle \mathcal{S}, \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{P}, s_0, r^e, \gamma \rangle$ as set out in the main text. Let $G^e(\tau)$ denote the cumulative environment reward of a single trajectory $\tau = \langle s_0, a_0, \dots, s_T \rangle$ where T is the total time of the trajectory, we have

$$G^e(\tau) = \sum_{t=0}^T \gamma^t r^e(s_t, a_t). \quad (3)$$

A policy π_θ is a conditional distribution $\pi : \mathcal{S} \rightarrow \Delta(\mathcal{A})$ parameterized by θ , where $\Delta(\cdot)$ denotes the space of probability distribution. The probability of a trajectory τ being generated, given that actions come from π_θ and the starting state is s_0 , is expressed as:

$$P(\tau | \pi_\theta) = \prod_{t=0}^T \mathcal{P}(s_{t+1} | s_t, a_t) \pi_\theta(a_t | s_t) \quad (4)$$

Because a policy π is stochastic, different trajectories could be generated from the same policy for a given initial state. The objective function to be optimized is the expected cumulative environment reward of trajectories generated by π starting from state s_0 . It is also called the state value function of s_0 and denoted as:

$$V^\pi(s_0) := \mathbb{E}_{\rho_s^\pi} [G^e(\tau)] = \sum_{\text{all } \tau_i \text{ generated by } \pi_\theta} G^e(\tau_i) \cdot P(\tau_i | \pi) \quad (5)$$

where ρ_s^π denotes the trajectory **distribution** of s_0, a_0, s_1, \dots induced by running π starting from $s_0 = s$. We defined an acceptable policy π_A as

$$\pi_A : V^{\pi_A} \geq V^{\pi^*} - \epsilon \quad (6)$$

where π^* is the optimal policy and ϵ is a control parameter that quantifies the acceptance of other policies. Acceptable policies defined in this way are also referred to as ϵ -optimal policies. We set $V^* = V^{\pi^*}$ for easy reference. Any policy that is not an acceptable policy is an unacceptable policy π_U . We define a good trajectory τ_G as

$$\tau_G : G^e(\tau_G) \geq V^* - \epsilon. \quad (7)$$

Any trajectory that is not a good trajectory is a bad trajectory τ_B . Note that this way of distinguishing good/bad trajectories and acceptable/unacceptable policies is explicitly based on the environment reward r^e , and introducing additional or alternative rewards into the system does not change this definition. For easy reference, we call any trajectory that reaches a goal state a goal trajectory, and we call any policy that can generate at least one goal trajectory a goal policy.

We denote the state distribution of a policy π at time t as d_t^π . Thus, the **discounted average state distribution** of a policy π can be expressed as $d^\pi = (1 - \gamma) \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \gamma^t d_t^\pi$, where $(1 - \gamma)$ is the normalization factor to ensure the result is a proper probability distribution. We also define a shorthand notation – for a state distribution $d \in \Delta(\mathcal{S})$, we define $V(d) = \mathbb{E}_{s \sim d} [V(s)]$.

When the Heuristic-Guided Reinforcement Learning (HuRL) framework is applied, the reshaped MDP $\widetilde{\mathcal{M}}$ has separated reshaped reward \widetilde{r} and separated discount factor $\widetilde{\gamma} = \beta\gamma$, where $\beta \in [0, 1]$ is the hyperparameter that scales the auxiliary heuristic rewards. We denote the value function of the reshaped MDP as \widetilde{V} , and the optimal policy and its value function under $\widetilde{\mathcal{M}}$ as $\widetilde{\pi}^*$ and $\widetilde{V}^*(\widetilde{V}^{\pi^*})$.

The discussion regarding the convergence guarantee of learning π in $\widetilde{\mathcal{M}}$ resulting in the optimal policy in the original MDP \mathcal{M} can be found in Appendix C1. For the purposes of this paper, it is sufficient to note that the authors of HuRL have provided a trick to ensure convergence. Moreover, empirical experiments conducted by the authors demonstrate that HuRL converges even without this trick.

It is also important to distinguish the Bellman backup equation under the two different MDPs: the original \mathcal{M} and the reshaped $\widetilde{\mathcal{M}}$. By definition, $(\mathcal{B}h)(s, a) = r(s, a) + \gamma \mathbb{E}_{s' \sim \mathcal{P}(\cdot | s, a)} [h(s')]$. In contrast, $(\widetilde{\mathcal{B}}h)(s, a) = \widetilde{r}(s, a) + \widetilde{\gamma} \mathbb{E}_{s' \sim \mathcal{P}(\cdot | s, a)} [h(s')]$. Nevertheless, the two Bellman backup equations possess a remarkable property – they are essentially equivalent to each other:

$$\begin{aligned} (\widetilde{\mathcal{B}}h)(s, a) &= \widetilde{r}(s, a) + \widetilde{\gamma} \mathbb{E}_{s' \sim \mathcal{P}(\cdot | s, a)} [h(s')] \\ &= (r(s, a) + (1 - \beta)\gamma \mathbb{E}_{s' \sim \mathcal{P}(\cdot | s, a)} [h(s')]) + \beta\gamma \mathbb{E}_{s' \sim \mathcal{P}(\cdot | s, a)} [h(s')] \\ &= r(s, a) + \gamma \mathbb{E}_{s' \sim \mathcal{P}(\cdot | s, a)} [h(s')] \\ &= (\mathcal{B}h)(s, a) \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

3) *Detailed Construction of Markovian Heuristic using Non-Markovian Rewards from VLM:* Specifically,

$$h(s_t) := \begin{cases} A(s_t)V^*(s_t) & \text{if } s_t \in S^{m(t)} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

where

$$A(s_t) := \frac{\prod_{t'=0}^t r^v(\tau_{t'}, l_{m(t')})}{\prod_{t'=0}^t r^v(\tau_{t'}^*, l_{m(t')})} \in [0, 1] \quad (10)$$

is a scaling factor that quantifies how closely the agent is following previous instructions.

B. Theoretical Analysis and Proofs

1) *Convergence time on a sparse-reward landscape:* We can pin down a characteristic convergence time on a sparse-reward landscape. The sparse-reward setting enforces that

$$r^e(s_t) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } s_t \in \mathcal{S}_G \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}. \quad (11)$$

It is clear from the definition that a good trajectory must always be a goal trajectory, and the cumulative reward is simply the reward at the final goal state so $G^e(\tau) = \gamma^T$ in this setting. For a randomly initialized policy, it is highly unlikely that the initial distribution of trajectories contains any goal trajectory due to the sparsity of goal states. The optimization of $V_{\pi_\theta}^e$ thus consists of two parts. The first part is to search for a goal trajectory. The gradient landscape is almost 0 everywhere, except for cases where a trajectory is δ -close to a goal trajectory. Here δ is the differential unit in the numerical differentiation used in the gradient calculation

$$\theta = \theta + \alpha \nabla_\theta V_{\pi_\theta} \quad (12)$$

such that δ -close means being numerically accessible within a distance of $|\delta|$ in parameter space. And the second part is to reduce T so that goal trajectories become good trajectories and consequently achieving acceptable policies. For the first part, searching for a trajectory for the target is effectively a random walk in the d -dimensional parameter space due to the flat gradient landscape.

Lemma A.2. *For a random walk in n -dimensional space, the expected number of steps T_D needed to travel a distance of D scales with D^2 .*

Proof: let $\vec{X}_1, \vec{X}_2, \dots, \vec{X}_T$ be IID random unit vectors uniformly distributed on a $(d-1)$ -dimensional sphere $\mathcal{S}^{d-1} \subset \mathbb{R}^d$, where $\vec{X}_i = (X_{i1}, \dots, X_{id})$ and $|\vec{X}_i|^2 = \sum_{j=1}^d X_{ij}^2 = 1$. Let $\vec{S}_T := \sum_{i=1}^T \vec{X}_i$. By a n -dimensional cosine rule we have

$$|\vec{S}_T|^2 = |\vec{S}_{T-1}|^2 + 2\vec{S}_{T-1} \cdot \vec{X}_T + |\vec{X}_T|^2, \quad (13)$$

and because $\mathbb{E}[\vec{X}_T] = \vec{0}$

$$\mathbb{E}[|\vec{S}_T|^2] = \mathbb{E}[|\vec{S}_{T-1}|^2] + \mathbb{E}[2\vec{S}_{T-1} \cdot \vec{X}_T] + 1 \quad (14)$$

$$= \mathbb{E}[|\vec{S}_{T-1}|^2] + 2\vec{S}_{T-1} \mathbb{E}[\vec{X}_T] + 1 \quad (15)$$

$$= \mathbb{E}[|\vec{S}_{T-1}|^2] + 1 \quad (16)$$

$$= \mathbb{E}[|\vec{S}_{T-2}|^2] + 1 + 1 \quad (17)$$

$$\vdots \quad (18)$$

$$= T \quad (19)$$

i.e. $\mathbb{E}[|\vec{S}_T|] \sim \sqrt{T}$. When a policy is randomly initialized with θ_0 , the distance D to a goal policy, $D := \|\theta_{goal} - \theta_0\|$ is fixed and is the distance the random walk needs to travel ($\mathbb{E}[|\vec{S}_T|] = D \sim \sqrt{T_D}$), so the characteristic time needed to travel this distance $T_D \sim D^2$ as we have shown above.

Assumption IV.1. Expert knowledge can guide the parameter search along a path in parameter space, defined by a sequence of n intermediate parameter vectors $\theta_1, \dots, \theta_n$, where each θ_i represents the parameters after learning sub-task l_i . As a result, the overall distance D can be decomposed into segments: $D \approx \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} d_k$, where $d_k = \|\theta_{k+1} - \theta_k\|$.

Auxiliary rewards essentially open the path for a divide-and-conquer approach by introducing intermediate rewards in the learning process. We introduce BiMI rewards as

$$r_{\text{BiMI}}^v(\tau, l_k) = \max(\mathbf{1}_{\{p(l_k|\tau) \geq \hat{q}\}} - p(l_k), 0) \quad (20)$$

and the cumulative reward of a single trajectory in the presence of BiMI rewards becomes

$$G_{\text{BiMI}}^v(\tau) = \sum_{t=0}^T \gamma^t r_{\text{BiMI}}^v(\tau, l_m(t)). \quad (21)$$

Because r_{BiMI}^v is either $1-p(l_k)$ or 0, it effectively breaks the entire task into n segments of sub-tasks $\{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n\}$ and each sub-task is a sparse-reward problem. Because this decomposition is based on expert knowledge, we can reasonably assume that the start-finish distance D in parameter space is partitioned into $D \approx d_1 + d_2 + \dots + d_{n-1}$ without incurring much detour (Assumption IV.1.)

Proposition IV.2. *The sum of expected time for a series of random walks, each covering the shorter distance of an individual sub-task, is less than the expected time to travel the entire distance D in one long random walk:*

$$\frac{1}{n-1} \mathbb{E}[T_D] \leq \mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{i=1}^{n-1} T_{d_i} \right] < \mathbb{E}[T_D].$$

Proof: the expected time taken for each of the sub-tasks then scales with d_i^2 respectively (Lemma A.2), and we have

$$d_1^2 + d_2^2 + \dots + d_{n-1}^2 < (d_1 + d_2 + \dots + d_{n-1})^2 \quad (22)$$

$$\mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{i=1}^{n-1} T_{d_i} \right] < \mathbb{E}[T_D] \quad (23)$$

because $d_i > 0 \forall i$. We can also work out that the upper bound for this improvement is a factor of $n-1$ by invoking the Cauchy-Schwarz inequality $(\sum_{i=1}^n u_i^2) (\sum_{i=1}^n v_i^2) \geq (\sum_{i=1}^n u_i v_i)^2$:

$$(d_1^2 + d_2^2 + \dots + d_{n-1}^2)(1^2 + 1^2 + \dots + 1^2) \geq (d_1 + d_2 + \dots + d_{n-1})^2 \quad (24)$$

$$(d_1^2 + d_2^2 + \dots + d_{n-1}^2) \geq \frac{1}{n-1} D^2 \quad (25)$$

$$\mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{i=1}^{n-1} T_{d_i} \right] \geq \frac{1}{n-1} \mathbb{E}[T_D] \quad (26)$$

and the equality sign holds (indicating maximal improvement) when $d_1 = d_2 = \dots = d_{n-1}$. The intuitive interpretation is that the divide-and-conquer approach is the most effective when the task is divided evenly into subtasks. Additionally, the presence of $p(l_k)$ introduces some lexical-level tolerance in the learning process and results in a considerably larger δ -close radius which could result in further improvement in the convergence rate. However, as we will discuss in the next section, introducing too much tolerance could harm the convergence rate rather than improve it.

2) False Positive and the Violation of Pessimistic Property of Heuristics:

Proposition IV.7. *Even if the heuristic remains conservative for all successor states, a single overestimation ($h(s) > V^*(s)$) can violate the pessimistic condition by causing $\max_a (\mathcal{B}h)(s, a) < h(s)$.*

Proof. We want to show that given:

- 1) for all successor states s' : $h(s') \leq V^*(s')$ for an arbitrary s .
- 2) false positive at current arbitrary state s : $V^*(s) < h(s)$.

The objective is to show that under the above conditions, we obtain $\max_a (\mathcal{B}h)(s, a) < h(s)$.

- 1) **Express the Bellman backup for h :** $(\mathcal{B}h)(s, a) = R(s, a) + \gamma \sum_{s'} P(s'|s, a) h(s')$
- 2) **Express the Bellman version of V^* :** $V^*(s) = \max_{a \in \mathcal{A}} [R(s, a) + \gamma \sum_{s'} P(s'|s, a) V^*(s')]$.

Given that $h(s') \leq V^*(s')$ for all s' , we can expand it to $\sum_{s'} \mathcal{P}(s'|s, a) h(s') \leq \sum_{s'} \mathcal{P}(s'|s, a) V^*(s')$. Therefore, we have:

$$R(s, a) + \gamma \sum_{s'} \mathcal{P}(s'|s, a) h(s') \leq R(s, a) + \gamma \sum_{s'} \mathcal{P}(s'|s, a) V^*(s') = Q^*(s, a) \quad (27)$$

3) **Taking the maximum over actions to both sides**, we have:

$$\max_a \left(R(s, a) + \gamma \sum_{s'} \mathcal{P}(s'|s, a) h(s') \right) \leq \max_a Q^*(s, a) \quad (28)$$

$$\max_a (\mathcal{B}h)(s, a) \leq V^*(s) \quad (29)$$

4) **Apply false positive condition:** Given $V^*(s) < h(s)$, substituting into the above inequality, we have $\max_a (\mathcal{B}h)(s, a) < h(s)$

Implication: Maintaining a pessimistic heuristic is inherently fragile because the introduction of a false positive in any state disrupts the pessimistic condition. \square

Theorem IV.8. *Borrowing from [1], the performance gap in RL when using heuristics can be broken down into a regret term and a bias term, where false negatives maintain the upper bound of bias while false positives increase the bias by breaking the heuristic's pessimism, thereby potentially leading to slower convergence.*

We analyze the convergence speed of policy learning by examining the performance gap, which is defined as the difference between the optimal value of the initial state s_0 , $V^*(s_0)$, and the value of the initial state under an arbitrary policy π , $V^\pi(s_0)$. Specifically, we focus on deriving an upper bound for this performance gap. The key intuition is that a smaller upper bound implies faster convergence to the optimal policy, as fewer iterations of policy updates will be required to reach the optimum.

We begin by stating the theorem made by HuRL authors:

Theorem A.3 (Performance Gap Decomposition [1]). *For any policy π , heuristic $h : \mathcal{S} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, and mixing coefficient $\beta \in [0, 1]$,*

$$V^*(s_0) - V^\pi(s_0) = \text{Regret}(h, \beta, \pi) + \text{Bias}(h, \beta, \pi) \quad (30)$$

where the regret and the bias term are expressed as follows:

$$\text{Regret}(h, \beta, \pi) := \beta \left(\tilde{V}^*(s_0) - \tilde{V}^\pi(s_0) \right) + \frac{1 - \beta}{1 - \gamma} \left(\tilde{V}^*(d^\pi) - \tilde{V}^\pi(d^\pi) \right) \quad (31)$$

$$\text{Bias}(h, \beta, \pi) := \left(V^*(s_0) - \tilde{V}^*(s_0) \right) + \frac{\gamma(1 - \beta)}{1 - \gamma} \mathbb{E}_{s, a \sim d^\pi} \mathbb{E}_{s' \sim \mathcal{P}(\cdot|s, a)} \left[h(s') - \tilde{V}^*(s') \right] \quad (32)$$

We will not provide a proof for Theorem A.3 in this paper. Please refer to [1] for details. The theorem demonstrates that the performance gap can be elegantly decomposed into two components: a regret term and a bias term such that:

- 1) The regret term quantifies the difference between \tilde{V}^* and \tilde{V}^π , representing the error caused by π being suboptimal in the reshaped MDP $\tilde{\mathcal{M}}$. Since π is trained by our selected RL algorithm directly on the reshaped MDP $\tilde{\mathcal{M}}$, the primary responsibility for minimizing this regret term falls to the RL algorithm itself, not to the design of the auxiliary reward signal. Thus, when evaluating the effects of false positive or false negative rewards, we choose not to focus on bounding the regret term.
- 2) The bias term captures two key discrepancies: first, between the true optimal value function V^* of the original MDP \mathcal{M} and the optimal value function \tilde{V}^* of the reshaped MDP $\tilde{\mathcal{M}}$; second, between \tilde{V}^* and the heuristic $h(s)$. This term, therefore, reflects the error introduced by addressing the reshaped MDP instead of the original one, alongside how well the heuristic h approximates the optimal value function in the reshaped MDP. Consequently, this bias term directly relates to the quality of the heuristic reward signal h . Hence, we focus on analyzing its upper bound to assess the impact of false positive or false negative rewards on this heuristic.

[1] have further derived the upper bound for the bias term, which we present here as a lemma. We omit the proof for brevity; for detailed proof, please refer to [1].

Lemma A.4 (Upper Bound of the Bias Term).

$$\text{Bias}(h, \beta, \pi) \leq (1 - \beta) \gamma \left(\mathbb{E}_{\rho^{\pi^*}} \left[\sum_{t=1}^{\infty} (\beta \gamma)^{t-1} (V^*(s_t) - h(s_t)) \right] + \mathbb{E}_{\rho^\pi} \left[\sum_{t=1}^{\infty} \gamma^{t-1} (h(s_t) - \tilde{V}^*(s_t)) \right] \right) \quad (33)$$

where ρ^π denotes the trajectory **distribution** of s_0, a_0, s_1, \dots induced by running π starting from s_0 .

This upper bound elegantly illustrates a trade-off: if the heuristic h is set too high (overestimation error), it reduces the first term but increases the second term. Conversely, if h is set too low (underestimation error), it increases the first term but reduces the second term. Just by inspection, it is not immediately clear whether overestimation or underestimation results in a better upper bound, as both impact the bias term in opposing ways.

We now prove that underestimation of h (pessimistic h) is better than overestimation (i.e., $\exists s_t \in \mathcal{S}, h(s_t) > V^*(s_t)$) for minimizing bias.

Proof. 1) **Define Terms:**

- Let $B_1 = \mathbb{E}_{\rho^{\pi^*}} \left[\sum_{t=1}^{\infty} (\beta\gamma)^{t-1} (V^*(s_t) - h(s_t)) \right]$
- Let $B_2 = \mathbb{E}_{\rho^{\pi}} \left[\sum_{t=1}^{\infty} \gamma^{t-1} (h(s_t) - \tilde{V}^*(s_t)) \right]$

2) **Underestimation Case (Pessimistic h):**

Lemma A.5. *If h is pessimistic with respect to \mathcal{M} , $\forall \beta \in [0, 1], s \in \mathcal{S}, \tilde{V}^*(s) \geq h(s)$*

Proof. To begin with, we need to use another lemma from [1], shown as follows:

Lemma A.6 (Bellman backup of reshaped MDP [1]). *For any policy π , we have*

$$\tilde{V}^{\pi}(s_0) - h(s_0) = \frac{1}{1 - \beta\gamma} \mathbb{E}_{\tilde{d}_{s_0}^{\pi}} [(\tilde{\mathcal{B}}h)(s, a) - h(s)] \quad (34)$$

where $\tilde{d}_{s_0}^{\pi}$ refers to the **discounted average state distribution** of policy π in reshaped MDP $\tilde{\mathcal{M}}$. It can be expressed as $\tilde{d}_{s_0}^{\pi} = (1 - \tilde{\gamma}) \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \tilde{\gamma}^t d_t^{\pi}$, and d_t^{π} is the state distribution of policy π at time t with $d_0^{\pi} = \mathbf{1}\{s = s_0\}$.

For brevity, we do not include the proof for Lemma A.6.

First of all, due to the definition of optimal value V^* , we have

$$\tilde{V}^*(s_0) \geq \tilde{V}^{\pi}(s_0) \quad (35)$$

Then, according to Lemma A.6, we can get

$$\tilde{V}^*(s_0) \geq \tilde{V}^{\pi}(s_0) = h(s_0) + \frac{1}{1 - \beta\gamma} \mathbb{E}_{\tilde{d}_{s_0}^{\pi}} [(\tilde{\mathcal{B}}h)(s, a) - h(s)] \quad (36)$$

Let π denote the greedy policy of $\arg \max_a (\mathcal{B}h)(s, a)$ and then trace back to Equation 8, we have $(\tilde{\mathcal{B}}h)(s, a) = (\mathcal{B}h)(s, a)$, that means

$$\tilde{V}^*(s_0) \geq \tilde{V}^{\pi}(s_0) = h(s_0) + \frac{1}{1 - \beta\gamma} \mathbb{E}_{\tilde{d}_{s_0}^{\pi}} [(\tilde{\mathcal{B}}h)(s, a) - h(s)] \quad (37)$$

$$= h(s_0) + \frac{1}{1 - \beta\gamma} \mathbb{E}_{\tilde{d}_{s_0}^{\pi}} [(\mathcal{B}h)(s, a) - h(s)] \quad (38)$$

$$\geq h(s_0) \quad [\text{direct result of } h \text{ being pessimistic}] \quad (39)$$

Generalization to Any State: The lemma from [1] (Lemma A.6) is stated in terms of any starting state s_0 . Therefore, we can replace s_0 with any state $s \in \mathcal{S}$ in our analysis. Thus we get $\forall s \in \mathcal{S}, \tilde{V}^*(s) \geq h(s)$ \square

Lemma A.5 implies that when h is pessimistic, $B_2 = \mathbb{E}_{\rho^{\pi}} \left[\sum_{t=1}^{\infty} \gamma^{t-1} (h(s_t) - \tilde{V}^*(s_t)) \right] \leq 0$ because $\tilde{V}^*(s) \geq h(s)$ for all s . Therefore, the bias error is only bounded by B_1 when h is pessimistic, i.e., $\text{Bias}(h, \beta, \pi) \leq B_1$.

3) **Overestimation Case** ($\exists s_t \in \mathcal{S}, h(s_t) > V^*(s_t)$):

We show briefly that, unlike the underestimation error, the overestimation error does not have a closed-form upper bound expression. The difficulty, as pointed out by [1], originates from the trajectory-dependence on $\mathbb{E}_{\rho^{\pi}}[\cdot]$ as the l_{∞} approximation error here can be difficult to control in large state spaces. It is possible that, upon picking up falsely high h states, ρ^{π} gets further distorted away from ρ^{π^*} and accumulates more falsely high h states. In other words, this trajectory dependence makes B_2 prone to a feedback loop of accumulating overestimation errors and resulting in a much larger upper bound for the bias. \square

C. Additional Notes on Theoretical Setting

1) *Convergence Guarantee of HuRL Compared With Potential-Based Reward Shaping:* Previous work on potential-based reward shaping (PBRS) has established that learning a policy on a reshaped MDP can converge to the optimum of the original MDP, as proved by [2]. They proved that the optimal Q value of the reshaped MDP is equivalent to the optimal Q value of the original MDP minus a state-dependent function. Consequently, for an optimal policy defined as $\pi^* = \arg \max_{a \in \mathcal{A}} Q^*(s, a)$, this additional state-dependent value does not alter the policy. Thus, the optimal policy of the original MDP \mathcal{M} is also the optimal policy for the reshaped $\tilde{\mathcal{M}}$. However, the theoretical convergence for the reshaped MDP within the framework of Heuristic-Guided Reinforcement Learning (HuRL) has not been proven with the same rigor.

The authors of HuRL made a trick which involves manipulating the coefficient β , which scales the heuristic-based auxiliary rewards. If β increases gradually from 0 to 1 over the training process, the agent effectively transitions from interacting with the modified MDP back to the original MDP. This method ensures that, at the end of training, the agent is exactly solving

the original problem. Moreover, according to the Blackwell optimal property [3], convergence can occur before β reaches 1, thereby allowing the trained policy to maintain optimality in the original MDP under HuRL.

However, in the original HuRL paper, among the five test environments, the β hyperparameter was actually fixed for four of them. Surprisingly, HuRL still converged to the optimal policy faster than the original MDP without updating β . This observation poses an enigma within the HuRL framework, as it is unclear why this convergence to the optimum of the original MDP occurs without dynamically adjusting β .

Thus, while the practical success of HuRL in these environments is evident, the underlying reasons for such convergence remain to be fully understood. This discrepancy between theoretical expectation and empirical results leaves room for future research to explore why HuRL converges under fixed β . Nevertheless, proving the convergence properties goes beyond the scope of our paper, which aims to highlight the prevalence of false positive rewards and their impact. An alternative perspective on this issue is to consider the learning process of maximizing auxiliary rewards as akin to performing behavior cloning from experts. In this sense, we do not need to focus on convergence within the current MDP but can view it as a form of pretraining.

D. Implementation Details of the Experiments

1) *Environment Details:* We describe each testing environment used in our experiments. More details introduction can be found in on the official project homepage of each benchmark [4]–[6].

- **Crafter** features randomly generated 2D worlds where the player needs to forage for food and water, find shelter to sleep, defend against monsters, collect materials, and build tools. The original Crafter environment does not have a clear goal trajectory or instructions; agents are aimed at surviving as long as possible and exploring the environment to unlock new crafting recipes. We modified the environment to include a preset linear sequence of instructions to guide the agent to mine diamond. However, this instruction was found to hinder the agent’s performance. The nature of the task requires dynamic strategies and real-time decision-making, but the fixed instructions limited the agent. For example, the instruction did not account for what to do when the agent is attacked by zombies.
- **Montezuma’s Revenge** is a classic adventure platform game where the player must navigate through a series of rooms to collect treasures and keys. The game is known for its sparse rewards and challenging exploration requirements. We manually annotate 97 instructions for the agent to follow, guiding it to conquer the game. The instructions were designed to guide the agent through the game’s key challenges, such as avoiding enemies, collecting keys, and unlocking doors.
- **Minigrid ‘Go to seq’ Task:** We use the ‘Go to seq’ task in the Minigrid environment, where the agent must navigate through a sequence of rooms and touch target objects in the correct order. This is a sparse reward task where the agent receives a reward of 1 only upon completing the entire sequence correctly. During the training phase, we randomly generate 50 different tasks, each with a room size of 5, 3 rows, and 3 columns. Each task features a unique room layout and target object sequence. The instruction complexity is set to 3, meaning there are at least 3 target objects to interact with in a specific order.

Montezuma and Instructions

	Room	x	y
1	Goal		
2	climb down the middle ladder	1	74 192
3	jump right to the yellow rope	1	109 199
4	jump right to the right platform	1	133 192
5	climb down the right ladder	1	133 148
6	jump over the skull to its left	1	76 151
7	climb up the left ladder	1	21 192
8	jump up to grab the key	1	13 209
9	jump left to the left roof	1	44 235

Fig. 8: Illustration of the Montezuma’s Revenge task. The agent must navigate through a series of rooms to collect treasures and keys.

Minigrid and Instructions

1	Goal
2	go to the grey door after you go to the blue door and go to the purple door
3	go to the box, then go to the yellow ball and go to a red door
4	go to the purple door and go to the purple door, then go to the red box
5	go to the green box, then go to a box
6	go to the ball and go to the yellow door after you go to a grey door
7	go to a ball, then go to the blue ball

Fig. 9: Illustration of the Minigrid ‘Go to seq’ task. The agent must navigate through a sequence of rooms and touch target objects in the correct order.

Crafter and Instructions

1	Goal (Collect diamond)	
2	1. Collect wood	2. Collect wood again
3	3. Place table	4. Make wood pickaxe
4	5. Collect stone	6. Make stone pickaxe
5	7. Collect stone	8. Place furnace
6	9. Collect coal	10. Collect iron
7	11. Make iron pickaxe	12. Collect diamond

Fig. 10: Illustration of the Crafter task. The agent must survive as long as possible and explore for new crafting recipes.

2) *Instruction-Guide Procedure Details*: The VLM-based reward model will have a pointer to the sequence of the instruction sentence, starting at the first sentence. For original models *Pixl2R* and *ELLM-*, we follow the setting in their original work where for each instruction sentence (yes, the full instruction essay will be split into multiple sentences and treat each sentence as atomic instruction l_k), the reward model will have a maximum cap of rewards (2.0) it can assign to the agent in one episode. When the cap is reached, the reward model will move its pointer to the next instruction sentence. For the BiMI reward model, the reward model will move its pointer to the next instruction sentence when the binary signal is triggered. Below is the pseudo-code for the instruction-following RL training procedure for both *Pixl2R* and *ELLM-* models.

3) *Finetuning VLM-based Reward Models*: In contrast to previous work on instructing following RL where they rely on hand-crafted oracle multimodal reward models, we use actual pretrained VLMs to generate reward signals. 2 VLM backbone models are used in our experiments: 1) *CLIP* [7], pretrained by image-text pairs; and 2) *X-CLIP* [8], pretrained by video-text pairs. In particular, *Pixl2R* uses *CLIP* because it only uses the single latest frame as input. In contrast, *ELLM-* takes a slice of trajectory (i.e., multiple frames) as input, and thus uses either *X-CLIP* or *CLIP* with additional RNN encoder as the reward model.

Due to the cartoonish and abstract visuals of the testing environments, we need to further fine-tune the VLMs to adapt to this new visual domain. We use well-trained expert agents based on [9] to generate expert trajectories for the Crafter environments and annotate them with instructions using internal information from the game engine. For Minigrid environments, we use classical search-based planning robots to generate expert trajectories and annotate them with the corresponding task instructions. For Montezuma’s Revenge, we manually annotate the expert trajectories.

For Minigrid and Crafter, we have 80,000 training pairs, while for Montezuma’s Revenge, we have around 300 training pairs. These training data are of high quality, as we have made every effort to avoid false positive rewards due to poor training data

Algorithm 1 ELLM and Pixl2R pseudo-code for instruction-following RL

```
1: Initialize policy network  $\pi_\theta$ 
2: Initialize value network  $V_\phi$ 
3: Setup VLM-based reward model  $E(\cdot)$ 
4: Split instruction essay into sentences  $\{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_K\}$ 
5: Initialize instruction pointer  $p = 1$ 
6: Initialize cumulative VLM reward  $r_{\text{cum}} = 0$ 
7: Initialize cumulative VLM reward threshold  $q$ 
8: Initialize replay buffer  $\mathcal{D}$ 
9: Initialize agent trajectory memory queue  $\tau$  with length  $W$ 
10: for each episode do
11:   Initialize state  $s_0$ 
12:   for  $t = 0$  to  $T - 1$  do
13:     Select action  $a_t \sim \pi_\theta(a_t | s_t)$ 
14:     Execute  $a_t$ , observe next state  $s_{t+1}$  and extrinsic reward  $r_t^e$ 
15:     Enqueue  $(s_t, a_t, r_t, s_{t+1})$  in  $\tau$ 
16:     Compute VLM reward:
17:      $r_t^v = \frac{E(\tau) \cdot E(l_p)}{\|E(\tau)\| \|E(l_p)\|}$   $\triangleright$  Apply BiMI here if needed
18:     Combine rewards:  $r_t = r_t^e + (1 - \beta)\gamma r_t^v$   $\triangleright \beta$  is a scaling factor
19:     Store  $(s_t, a_t, r_t, s_{t+1})$  in  $\mathcal{D}$ 
20:      $r_{\text{cum}} \leftarrow r_{\text{cum}} + r_t^v$ 
21:     if  $r_{\text{cum}} \geq q$  then
22:        $p \leftarrow \min(p + 1, K)$ 
23:        $r_{\text{cum}} \leftarrow 0$ 
24:     if Reach Update Frequency then
25:       Sample mini-batch  $\{(s_j, a_j, r_j, s_{j+1})\}$  from  $\mathcal{D}$ 
26:       Compute TD errors:
27:        $\delta_j = r_j + \gamma V_\phi(s_{j+1}) - V_\phi(s_j)$ 
28:       Update value network:
29:        $\phi \leftarrow \phi + \alpha_v \sum_j \delta_j \nabla_\phi V_\phi(s_j)$ 
30:       Update policy network:
31:        $\theta \leftarrow \theta + \alpha_p \sum_j \delta_j \nabla_\theta \log \pi_\theta(a_j | s_j)$ 
```

quality. **To enhance our models' robustness, we also employed contrastive learning techniques during VLM training, utilizing similar manipulated data as hard negatives.** However, despite the fine-tuning process, false positive rewards remain unavoidable.

```

1 data_id,instruction,trajectory_chunk_file,trajectory_local_idx
2 0,climb down the middle ladder,montezuma/expert_traj_chunk_0.pkl,0
3 1,walk to the right side of the conveyor belt,montezuma/expert_traj_chunk_0
4 2,jump right to the yellow rope,montezuma/expert_traj_chunk_0.pkl,2
5 3,jump right to the right platform,montezuma/expert_traj_chunk_0.pkl,3
6 4,climb down the right ladder,montezuma/expert_traj_chunk_0.pkl,4
7 5,jump over the skull,montezuma/expert_traj_chunk_0.pkl,5
8 6,climb up the left ladder,montezuma/expert_traj_chunk_0.pkl,6
9 7,jump to grab the key,montezuma/expert_traj_chunk_0.pkl,7
10 8,jump left to the left roof ,montezuma/expert_traj_chunk_0.pkl,8
11 9,use key to open the left door,montezuma/expert_traj_chunk_0.pkl,9
12 10,walk left when the laser gate disappears,montezuma/expert_traj_chunk_0.p
13 11,walk to the middle when the laser gate disappears,montezuma/expert_traj_
14 12,wait until the laser gate disappears,montezuma/expert_traj_chunk_0.pkl,1
15 13,approach to the gem,montezuma/expert_traj_chunk_0.pkl,13
16 14,jump to grab the gem,montezuma/expert_traj_chunk_0.pkl,14
17 15,walk to the middle when the laser gate disappears,montezuma/expert_traj_
18 16,climb down the middle ladder,montezuma/expert_traj_chunk_0.pkl,16
19 17,wait until the spider goes away,montezuma/expert_traj_chunk_0.pkl,17

```

Fig. 11: Example of training data for the Montezuma environment.

We used the threshold \hat{q} introduced in Section VI-A to make binary classification on the testing pairs to evaluate the performance of the fine-tuned VLM-based reward models. We found that VLM models had difficulty achieving high accuracy on Minigrid environment, which is likely due to the too abstract and cartoonish nature of the environment, causing the VLMs to struggle to learn the visual-textual correspondence. We also found that X-CLIP did not perform better than CLIP in our experiments. We hypothesize that the cartoonish nature of the testing environments may have caused the X-CLIP model to struggle to learn the visual-textual correspondence. Thus, we used CLIP as the backbone model throughout our following experiments. The performance of the fine-tuned VLM-based reward models is shown in Table III. **Even when the precision score reaches 0.98, indicating that only 2% of the rewards are false positives in the validation set, the agent can still significantly underperform in the testing environments. The core issue is that in out-of-distribution (O.O.D.) testing environments, false positive rewards are prevalent and inevitable. Therefore, it is crucial to design a reward function that is robust to reward noise.**

TABLE III: Performance of fine-tuned VLM reward model on the testing dataset using the 90th percentile empirical quantile as threshold

Environment	Precision	Accuracy	F1 Score	Recall	Model
Crafter	0.9847	0.9466	0.8538	0.9702	CLIP ELLM-
Crafter	0.9799	0.9028	0.7618	0.9842	CLIP Pix12R
Crafter	0.2095	0.2514	0.2868	0.9657	XCLIP ELLM-
Minigrid	0.7260	0.9200	0.7849	0.9763	CLIP ELLM-
Minigrid	0.6992	0.9086	0.7592	0.9616	CLIP Pix12R
Minigrid	0.1716	0.2310	0.2642	0.9704	XCLIP ELLM-
Montezuma	0.8838	0.9638	0.8825	0.9478	CLIP ELLM-
Montezuma	0.8343	0.9108	0.7652	0.9842	CLIP Pix12R
Montezuma	0.8044	0.9259	0.8045	0.9657	XCLIP ELLM-

4) *Hyperparameters for Instruction-Following RL Agents:* In the experiments, all methods are implemented based on PPO with same model architecture. The Minigrid and Crafter environments use the same training hyperparameters as the Achievement Distillation paper [9]. For Montezuma’s Revenge, we found that the performance of the agent was sensitive to the gamma

and GAE lambda parameters. To improve the performance of agents in Montezuma’s Revenge, we took two additional steps: (1) normalizing the observation inputs when computing the rewards, and (2) not normalizing the advantage during the GAE calculation. The hyperparameters are shown in the following tables.

TABLE IV: Model Parameters

Parameter	Value
model_cls	“PPORNNModel”
hidsize	1024
gru_layers	1
impala_kwargs	
- chans	[64, 128, 128]
- outsize	256
- nblock	2
- post_pool_groups	1
- init_norm_kwargs	
- batch_norm	false
- group_norm_groups	1
dense_init_norm_kwargs	
- layer_norm	true

TABLE V: Crafter and Minigrid RL Parameters

Parameter	Value
gamma	0.95
gae_lambda	0.65
algorithm_cls	“PPOAlgorithm”
algorithm_kwargs	
- ppo_nepoch	3
- ppo_nbatch	8
- clip_param	0.2
- vf_loss_coef	0.5
- ent_coef	0.01
- lr	3.0e-4
- max_grad_norm	0.5
- aux_freq	8
- aux_nepoch	6
- pi_dist_coef	1.0
- vf_dist_coef	1.0

TABLE VI: Montezuma RL Training Parameters

Parameter	Value
gamma	0.99
gae_lambda	0.95
int_rew_type	“rnd”
pre_obs_norm_steps	50
algorithm_cls	“PPOAlgorithm”
algorithm_kwargs	
- update_proportion	0.25
- ppo_nepoch	3
- ppo_batch_size	256
- clip_param	0.1
- vf_loss_coef	0.5
- ent_coef	0.001
- lr	1.0e-4

E. Additional Details of the Experiments on the Impact of Noisy Rewards

Evaluation Metric Details In our experiments, we used a score metric adapted from the Crafter paper to evaluate agent performance across different environments. This score metric aggregates success rates for individual subtasks using a geometric mean. Formally, the score metric is defined as follows:

$$\text{Score} = \exp \left(\frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N \ln(1 + s_k) \right) - 1 \quad (40)$$

where s_k is the agent’s success rate of achieving instruction l_k , and N is the total number of instructions.

This metric was chosen over the *maximum total rewards* metric for several reasons:

- 1) **Consistency in Sparse Reward Settings:** Sparse reward environments often pose significant challenges for reinforcement learning agents. An agent might occasionally achieve high rewards by chance in one rollout but fail to replicate this success consistently in subsequent rollouts. This variability can lead to misleading evaluations if only the maximum total rewards are considered. The Score metric, by measuring the success rate of achieving each subgoal, provides a more stable and consistent measure of an agent’s performance.
- 2) **Capturing Learning Stability:** The Score metric evaluates the agent’s ability to consistently reproduce successful behaviors across multiple episodes. This is crucial in sparse reward settings, where the agent’s performance can fluctuate significantly. By focusing on the success rates of individual subtasks, the Score metric offers a more granular and reliable assessment of the agent’s learning progress and stability.
- 3) **Crafter Benchmark Standard:** The Crafter benchmark, which introduces the Score metric, is a well-regarded standard.

Crafter codebase provides *score* metric calculation by default. For Minigrid and Montezuma environments, we use the internal information from the game engine to detect whether the subtasks are completed, thus facilitating the calculation of the *score* metric.

1) *Details of Manipulated Trajectory-Instruction Pairs to Evaluate Robustness* : We evaluated the models’ sensitivity by examining how cosine similarity scores change for manipulated trajectory-instruction pairs. These manipulations were designed to test the robustness of the models against various types of noise. Here’s a detailed breakdown of the manipulations:

- 1) **Trajectory Reversal:** We inverted the sequence of frames within each trajectory (i.e., `frames = frame[::-1]`) to assess the model’s ability to detect reversed state transitions. This manipulation tests whether the model can distinguish between forward and backward progression in the state transition.
- 2) **Instruction Negation:** We modified the original instructions by adding negation (e.g., changing “do l_k ” to “do not do l_k ” or “avoid l_k ”). This tests the model’s sensitivity to semantic changes in the instruction that fundamentally alter the goal.
- 3) **Instruction Rephrasing:** We rephrase the original instructions while maintaining their core meaning. This evaluates the model’s robustness to linguistic variations and its ability to capture the essential semantic content of instructions.
- 4) **Concatenation and Order Swapping:** Given two trajectory-instruction pairs (τ_1, l_1) and (τ_2, l_2) , we created concatenated pairs and then swapped the order in one modality. For example:

- Original concatenation: $(\tau_1 + \tau_2, l_1 + l_2)$
- Swapped trajectory: $(\tau_2 + \tau_1, l_1 + l_2)$
- Swapped instruction: $(\tau_1 + \tau_2, l_2 + l_1)$

This tests the model’s sensitivity to the order of components in multi-step tasks.

- 5) **Concatenation with Partial Content:** We concatenated pairs but truncated one modality. For instance:

- Truncated trajectory: $(\tau_1, l_1 + l_2)$
- Truncated instruction: $(\tau_1 + \tau_2, l_1)$

This assesses the model’s ability to detect partial mismatches in longer sequences.

F. Details of Showing the Prevalence of False Positives in VLM Cosine Similarity Scores

We list the figures of reward signals from learned VLMs for different types of trajectory-instruction pairs for each individual environment. All figures show that the VLM-based reward models assign high rewards to manipulated trajectory-instruction pairs, indicating the prevalence of false positive rewards.

Fig. 12: Cosine similarity scores for match, mismatch and manipulated trajectory-instruction pairs in Montezuma.

Fig. 13: Cosine similarity scores for match, mismatch and manipulated trajectory-instruction pairs in Minigrid.

Fig. 14: Cosine similarity scores for match, mismatch and manipulated trajectory-instruction pairs in Crafter.

G. Impact of Reward Model Quality on Policy Learning Efficiency: Supplementary Experiments and Quantitative Analysis in Montezuma

In our efforts to assess the impact of false positive rewards from auxiliary reward model without the interference of other factors such as domain shift, poor data quality, and errors from other issues such as the choice of multimodal architectures, we devised a **simulated** auxiliary reward model (also known as *oracle* auxiliary reward model) that access to internal state information from the game engine. The model compares the sequence of past actions and states of the agent with predefined target intermediate state sets that map to each instruction sentence. This is feasible in Montezuma’s Revenge environment as we are able to access coordinate system information directly from the game engine. This access allows us to locate the current positional information of the agent and also label specific intermediate states as targets and assign rewards to the agent accordingly.

We therefore designed three types of simulated reward model:

- **Sim RM 1 (Perfect)** generates rewards accurately whenever the agent reaches the designated intermediate states. Furthermore, it strictly adheres to the chronological sequence of instructions; rewards for subsequent instructions are only awarded if all preceding instructions have been fulfilled.
- **Sim RM 2 (False Positive)** introduces a tolerance for false positive rewards but with reduced reward magnitudes, all while maintaining the temporal sequence. This is implemented by defining a radius σ , where if the agent enters a circle centered at the target state with a radius of σ , it receives a small amount of rewards.
- **Sim RM 3 (Temporal Insensitive False Positive)** disregards the chronological order of instructions, allowing rewards for later tasks even if earlier ones remain unfulfilled. However, note that fulfilling every sub-task will still result in the agent receiving the maximum total rewards. Therefore, in theory, the policy will eventually converge.

Results are reported in Table VII. Several important observations are as follows:

TABLE VII: Agent performance in Montezuma’s Revenge, evaluated across three rooms with the goal state being the exit through a designated door. Metrics measured are the Area Under the Curve (AUC) for total reward (where higher is better) and success rate (SR) of reaching the goal state. The baseline is denoted as B, with \star marking statistical significance ($p < 0.05$).

Model	AUC	SR
(1) PPO [10]	all failed	0%
(2) PPO+RND (B) [11]	0.550±0.066	100%
(3) PPO + Sim RM 1 (Perfect)	0.287±0.048	100%
(4) PPO+RND + Sim RM 1 (Perfect)	0.608±0.073	100%
(5) PPO+RND + Sim RM 2 (False Positive)	0.183±0.187 \star	73.3%
(6) PPO+RND + Sim RM 3 (Temp. Insen.)	0.051±0.116 \star	16.7%

- Perfect auxiliary reward model have shown enhanced performance compared to weak RL baselines like PPO. While agents trained solely with PPO struggled to play Montezuma, incorporating Perfect auxiliary reward model into PPO (i.e., (3) in Table VII) did find the goal state, with the success rate increasing from 0% to 100%. However, we observed that the auxiliary reward model learns more slowly than the intrinsic reward model (see (2) in Table VII) when attempting to reach the goal state. This finding was initially surprising, but upon examining the agent movement heatmaps in Figure 15a and Figure 15b, an explanation becomes clear: the PPO+RND model discovers shorter paths to the goal state. The heatmap reveals that the PPO+RND agent learns to directly jump to a rope, bypassing the use of a ladder and conveyor belt as suggested by the expert instructions. This observation raises a concern about instruction-following based reward signals; they might limit the agent’s exploration, confining it to states favored by the expert. If the quality of the expert’s knowledge about the task is not optimal, this can result in the agent failing to compete with an exploration-based reward model.
- Again, we observed a remarkable synergy between the instruction-following-based reward model and the intrinsic reward model, as discussed in §VII-A. As shown in (4) in Table VII, the PPO+RND + Sim RM 1 (Perfect) agent achieves the highest AUC score, demonstrating that it learns to reach the goal state faster than any other model.
- The involvement of false positive rewards significantly slows down the learning process of the model, as evidenced by entries (5) and (6) in Table VII. Additionally, both (5) and (6) show lower AUC scores compared to (2), which is the vanilla PPO+RND model. If we consider the vanilla PPO+RND model to represent a scenario with **full false negative** instruction-following rewards (since no instruction-following reward model is implemented here), then comparing the scores of (2) with (5) and (6) further indicates that false positive rewards are **more detrimental** than false negative ones.
- The RL + VLM reward approach completely failed to converge when the reward model disregarded temporal ordering, as evidenced by entry (6) in Table VII. The success rate had a significant drop to 16.7%, and even the RND intrinsic reward was unable to recover the success rate within the time budget. This illustrates the severe impact of false positive rewards

due to temporal ordering insensitivity, an example of composition insensitivity discussed in §V; they trap the agent in a cycle of ineffective actions. However, note that if every sub-task is fulfilled, the agent will still receive the maximum total rewards, suggesting that, in theory, the policy could eventually converge. **Yet**, the practical implications of such false positives emphasize how they can drastically extend the learning period or lead to non-convergence in real-world scenarios where time or computational resources are limited.

(a) PPO+RND agent (same as + (b) PPO+RND + Sim RM 1 (Per- (c) PPO+RND + Sim RM 2 (False (d) PPO+RND + Sim RM 3 (Tem-
Sim RM (False Negative)) fect) Positive) poral Insensitivity)

Fig. 15: Movement heatmap for PPO+RND agents when different simulated auxiliary instruction-following-based reward models are involved.

We also provided movement heatmap of different models for further qualitative analysis. As shown in Figure 15a, intrinsic reward model explored a shortcut towards the goal state by directly jump from the initial state to the rope, thereby learning to reach the goal state faster than other models.

Figures 15b and 15c do not exhibit a significant contrast, but they do reveal that the presence of false positive rewards leads the agent to more frequently visit dead ends, such as falling off cliffs. This behavior is consistent with the mechanics of the simulated false positive reward model, which defines a radius σ around target states. Within this radius, even if an agent falls off a cliff, it might receive rewards because its position could be close enough to the intended intermediate rewarding state. Consequently, agents had a chance of mistakenly perceiving falling off as advantageous.

Figure 15d illustrates the consequences when temporal ordering restrictions are removed: the learning agent persistently pursues rewards associated with the final instruction, “walk left to the door.” However, simply executing this last instruction does not suffice for escaping the room because access to the door requires a key. This suggests that false positive rewards cause the agent to get trapped in local minima closer to s_0 , indicating that deep RL can easily hack the reward system and effectively exploit shortcuts [12]. A critical issue arises here: even with intrinsic rewards, the agent fails to escape these local optima, suggesting it has reached an equilibrium in the MDP where policy updates cease. This scenario is particularly relevant when the initial state distribution does not cover the entire state space. If the initial distribution does not have a positive probability for all states (i.e., $\forall s \in \mathcal{S}, d_0(s) > 0$), it is not guaranteed that the RL algorithm will eventually reach the global optimum with maximum total rewards, as highlighted by [13].

H. Pseudo-code for Empirical Quantile Calculation for Binary Signal Threshold

Using empirical quantile as threshold guarantees a high probability (at least $1 - \alpha$) that the true positive pairs are recognized while minimizing the average number of mistakes predicting false positives [14]:

Algorithm 2 Calculate Empirical Quantile (\hat{q})

Require: Calibration set $\{\tau, l\}_n$, where l is the instruction sentence, τ is the corresponding trajectory, and n is the number of samples;
 Significance level α ;
 VLM model reward model v

- 1: \triangleright Obtain the similarity-based score \triangleleft
 - 2: $\{r\}_n \leftarrow \{v(\tau, l)\}_n$
 - 3: \triangleright Compute the quantile level \triangleleft
 - 4: $q_{\text{level}} \leftarrow \frac{\lceil (n-1) \times (1-\alpha) \rceil}{n}$
 - 5: \triangleright Compute the empirical quantile \triangleleft
 - 6: $\hat{q} \leftarrow \text{np.quantile}(\{r\}_n, q_{\text{level}}, \text{method}='lower')$
 - 7: **return** \hat{q}
-

I. Implementation Details of the Experiments of BiMI Reward Function

We set confidence level for empirical quantile calculation to be $1 - \alpha = 0.9$. We adhered to the standard requirement of limiting the training budget to 1 million frames [6]. This constraint poses a significant challenge, particularly in sparse reward settings, as it demands that agents both explore efficiently and exploit their knowledge effectively within this limited budget.

To achieve the 1 million frame budget, we used the following configuration:

- `nproc`: 8 (Number of processes used for parallel environments)
- `nstep`: 512 (Length of the rollout stored in the buffer)
- `nepoch`: 250 (Number of epochs to train the RL policy)

This configuration results in approximately 1 million steps: $250 \text{ epochs} \times 512 \text{ steps} \times 8 \text{ processes} = 1,024,000 \text{ frames}$.

In the case of Montezuma’s Revenge, we found that the 1 million frame limit used in Crafter was insufficient due to the game’s complexity and sparse reward structure. To address this, we extended the training budget to 8 million frames. It’s important to note that even with this increased frame count, agents were still unable to fully solve the task. As [15] pointed out, about 1 billion frames are required to truly master Montezuma’s Revenge. This vast difference in required training time (8 million vs 1 billion frames) underscores the exceptional difficulty of Montezuma’s Revenge as a sparse reward task.

The implementation details for the BiMI reward function are consistent with those outlined in the first stage of experiments.

J. Detailed Experiment Results of BiMI Reward Function

Fig. 16: Besides the improvements of the score performance of agents across different environments with the BiMI reward function, it also collaborates well with intrinsic rewards. Combining both can lead to significant performance improvements

Fig. 17: Ablation on the components of BiMI reward function. The binary reward (Bi) alone led to a 36.5% improvement compared to original models. Excluding Crafter, Mutual Information (MI) provided a 23% further improvement over Bi alone

1) *Minigrid*: ELLM+BiMI achieved a remarkable 74% improvement in performance compared to the original models. This substantial gain is particularly noteworthy given the unique challenges presented by *Minigrid*. The abstract, shape-based visuals in *Minigrid* diverge drastically from the natural images used in VLMs’ pretraining, preventing the models from effectively utilizing their prior pretraining knowledge. Consequently, VLMs struggled to accurately assess similarities between *Minigrid*’s abstract visuals and textual instructions, resulting in highly noisy reward signals. The significant improvement demonstrated by BiMI underscores its effectiveness in handling noisy signals, directly addressing our primary research challenge. This capability is crucial for deploying instruction-following agents in real-world, unfamiliar scenarios, where visual inputs often deviate from the VLMs’ training distribution, leading to noisy reward signals.

2) *Crafter*: We observed an intriguing pattern of results. The Bi component alone led to 14% and 3.2% improvement in performance over the original models. However, contrary to our observations in other environments, the addition of the MI component actually decreased this improvement. This unexpected outcome can be attributed to the unique nature of *Crafter* task, where agents must repeatedly achieve the same subtasks (e.g., drinking water) for survival. The MI component, designed to discourage over-reliance on frequently occurring signals, inadvertently penalized the necessary repetition of survival-critical actions. Furthermore, note that instruction-following RL agents, regardless of the reward model employed, were unable to outperform pure RL agents in *Crafter*. This discrepancy is due to the open-world nature of *Crafter*, which requires dynamic strategies and real-time decision-making that our testing setups did not fully capture. Despite these challenges, it is noteworthy that Bi alone still managed to improve performance over vanilla VLM-based reward models, suggesting that reducing false positives is still beneficial across all testing environments. The combination of BiMI with *DEIR* (the intrinsic reward model) also showed promising results, indicating a productive balance between exploration (driven by *DEIR*) and exploitation (guided by BiMI instruction reward).

K. Alternative Proof of the Reduction of Convergence Rate

This section contains the convergence analysis based on the formal definition of Range Set of Acceptable Policies (Range-SOAP) and the categorization of policies into acceptable and unacceptable policies, which is a completely separate analysis from the main paper.

Formally, [16] defined that:

Theorem A.7 ([16]). *A reward function realizes a Range Set of Acceptable Policies (Range-SOAP) Π_G when there exists an $\epsilon \geq 0$ such that every $\pi_g \in \Pi_G$ is ϵ -optimal in start-state value, $V^*(s_0) - V^{\pi_g}(s_0) \leq \epsilon$, while all other policies are worse.*

When the reward signal is sparse, the agent only receives a reward upon reaching some goal states, and the reward function does not provide any feedback during the intermediate steps. We argue that the sparse reward function realizes a Range-SOAP, leading to the categorization of policies into acceptable and unacceptable policies.

Proposition A.8. *Sparse reward function “realizes” Range-SOAP (i.e., Range Set of Acceptable Policies).*

Justification:

A sparse reward function, where the agent only receives a reward upon completing the task, cannot prefer policies that lead to shorter task completion times. This is because either the agent completes the goal very quickly or slowly, they will receive nearly the same amount of cumulative rewards, and the reward function will not show a strong preference.

Since the sparse reward function does not induce a strict partial ordering on the policies, we say this reward function cannot realize a Partial Ordering (PO) task. Specifically, a PO on policies is a generalization of a Set of Acceptable Policies (SOAP) task. In a PO, the agent specifies a partial ordering on the policy space, where some policies are identified as “great”, some as “good”, and some as “bad” to strictly avoid, while remaining indifferent to the rest.

Therefore, the sparse reward function can realize a Set of Acceptable Policies (SOAP), where there is a set of policies that are all considered “good” or near-optimal, while all other policies are worse.

Furthermore, the sparse reward function will lead to a Range-SOAP, rather than an Equal-SOAP. Specifically, Equal-SOAP is a SOAP where all the acceptable policies are equally optimal in start-state value. This is because the good policies in the SOAP may differ slightly in their start-state values, as some may reach multiple goal states in the environment and thereby receiving different cumulative rewards. Therefore, the sparse reward function will realize a Range-SOAP, where there is a range of acceptable policies that are all near-optimal in start-state value.

This proposition forms the basis of our theoretical analysis in Section K.

Below is the convergence analysis when the total return can be classified by returns of trajectories from acceptable policies $P(\tau \in \mathcal{T}_G | \theta) \cdot \mathbb{E}[G(\tau) | \tau \in \mathcal{T}_G]$ versus returns of trajectories from unacceptable policies $P(\tau \in \mathcal{T}_B | \theta) \cdot \mathbb{E}[G(\tau) | \tau \in \mathcal{T}_B]$, where $\mathcal{T}_G \sim \Pi_G$, $\mathcal{T}_B \sim \Pi_B$ and $\Pi_B = \Pi \setminus \Pi_G$.

Note on Derivation: The proof presented here can be viewed as a reformulation of the Q-value function’s gradient in the context of our specific problem setup. While this derivation may appear straightforward to readers well-versed in reinforcement learning, we include it to provide a clear mathematical foundation for our analysis of false positive rewards in the VLM-RL context. This formulation helps bridge the gap between standard RL theory and our specific problem domain on instruction-following RL with VLM-based rewards.

Specifically, the update rule of Actor-Critic algorithm is:

- **Critic:**

$$\phi \leftarrow \phi - \alpha_\phi \nabla_\phi (\delta)^2 \quad (41)$$

where

$\delta = \mathbb{E}_{\pi_\theta} [G^{\pi_\theta} - Q_\phi(s, a)]$ is the Monte Carlo (MC) estimation error, $Q_\phi(s, a)$ is the Q-value function which measures the expected discounted cumulative reward given the state s and action a , and π_θ is the policy. G^{π_θ} is the rollout cumulative rewards from the trajectory τ^{π_θ} generated from π_θ .

- **Actor:**

$$\theta \leftarrow \theta + \alpha_\theta \frac{Q_\phi(s, a) \nabla_\theta \pi_\theta(a|s)}{\pi_\theta(a|s)} \quad (42)$$

We need to make the following assumptions to simplify the theoretical analysis:

- 1) We use \mathcal{T}_G to represent the set of acceptable trajectories and use \mathcal{T}_B as a non-overlapping set of “not acceptable” trajectories, we can say:

$$\mathcal{T}_G \cap \mathcal{T}_B = \emptyset \quad (43)$$

where \mathcal{T} is the trajectory distribution space of the agent policy π_θ .

2) When we define \mathcal{T}_B and \mathcal{T}_G within the universe \mathcal{T} , we must account for the possibility of a remaining set to ensure a complete partition of \mathcal{T} . The remaining set $\mathcal{T} \setminus (\mathcal{T}_B \cup \mathcal{T}_G)$ can be interpreted as a trajectories that partially fulfill the instruction. Given our focus on the influence of false positive rewards within challenging sequential decision-making tasks, we assume that partially correct trajectories are also **unacceptable**. This stance is justified by the fact that partially correct trajectories can be viewed as false positives: they appear to be plausible behaviors but ultimately fail to fulfill the instructions. Rewarding such trajectories could reinforce incomplete or potentially dangerous behaviors. The errors discussed in Section V can be seen as instances of partially correct trajectories that are ultimately unacceptable. For example, incompletely following a safety-critical task such as ‘‘turn off the machinery before performing maintenance’’ could pose significant risks, and rewarding such behavior would be undesirable. Consequently, for the purposes of our analysis, we can assume:

$$\mathcal{T}_G \cup \mathcal{T}_B = \mathcal{T} \quad (44)$$

- 3) Assume the policy class parameterized by θ should be expressive enough to capture optimal or near-optimal policies, and the policy is initialized randomly from uniform distribution, i.e., $\pi_{\theta_0} \sim \mathcal{U}(\Pi)$. Meanwhile, the Q-value is initialized as $Q_{\phi_0}(s, a) = 0, \forall s \in \mathcal{S} \forall a \in \mathcal{A}$.
- 4) We assume that $|\mathcal{T}_G|$ and $|\mathcal{T}_B|$ is a fixed number predefined by the task environment while $\mathbb{E}_{\tau \in \pi_{\theta}}[G(\tau) \mid \tau \in \mathcal{T}_B]$ is non-zero as false positive rewards are unavoidable in real-world VLMs.

Since the update rule for Q-value is a gradient descent on $\|\mathbb{E}_{\tau \in \pi_{\theta}}[G(\tau) - Q_{\phi}(s, a)]\|^2$, the updated Q-value will approach as follows:

$$Q_{\phi}(s, a) \rightarrow \mathbb{E}[G(\tau)] \quad (45)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= P(\tau \in \mathcal{T}_B \mid \theta) \cdot \mathbb{E}[G(\tau) \mid \tau \in \mathcal{T}_B] + P(\tau \in \mathcal{T}_G \mid \theta) \cdot \mathbb{E}[G(\tau) \mid \tau \in \mathcal{T}_G] \\ &\quad + P(\tau \in \mathcal{T} \setminus (\mathcal{T}_B \cup \mathcal{T}_G) \mid \theta) \cdot \mathbb{E}[G(\tau) \mid \tau \in \mathcal{T} \setminus (\mathcal{T}_B \cup \mathcal{T}_G)] \end{aligned} \quad (46)$$

$$= P(\tau \in \mathcal{T}_B \mid \theta) \cdot \mathbb{E}[G(\tau) \mid \tau \in \mathcal{T}_B] + P(\tau \in \mathcal{T}_G \mid \theta) \cdot \mathbb{E}[G(\tau) \mid \tau \in \mathcal{T}_G] \quad [\text{Assumption 2}] \quad (47)$$

$$(48)$$

Given that the update rule for policy π is the gradient ascent on $Q_{\phi}(s, a)\pi_{\theta}(a \mid s)$, we have the following:

$$\nabla_{\theta} Q_{\phi}(s, a)\pi_{\theta}(a \mid s) \quad (49)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= (\nabla_{\theta} P(\tau \in \mathcal{T}_B \mid \theta_{\text{old}}) \cdot \mathbb{E}[G(\tau) \mid \tau \in \mathcal{T}_B]\pi_{\theta}(a \mid s)) \\ &\quad + (\nabla_{\theta} P(\tau \in \mathcal{T}_G \mid \theta_{\text{old}}) \cdot \mathbb{E}[G(\tau) \mid \tau \in \mathcal{T}_G]\pi_{\theta}(a \mid s)) \end{aligned} \quad (50)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= P(\tau \in \mathcal{T}_B \mid \theta_{\text{old}}) \cdot \mathbb{E}[G(\tau) \mid \tau \in \mathcal{T}_B]\nabla_{\theta}\pi_{\theta}(a \mid s) \\ &\quad + P(\tau \in \mathcal{T}_G \mid \theta_{\text{old}}) \cdot \mathbb{E}[G(\tau) \mid \tau \in \mathcal{T}_G]\nabla_{\theta}\pi_{\theta}(a \mid s) \quad \theta_{\text{old}} \text{ terms are constants w.r.t. } \theta \end{aligned} \quad (51)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= (1 - P(\tau \in \mathcal{T}_G \mid \theta_{\text{old}})) \cdot \mathbb{E}[G(\tau) \mid \tau \in \mathcal{T}_B]\nabla_{\theta}\pi_{\theta}(a \mid s) \\ &\quad + P(\tau \in \mathcal{T}_G \mid \theta_{\text{old}}) \cdot \mathbb{E}[G(\tau) \mid \tau \in \mathcal{T}_G]\nabla_{\theta}\pi_{\theta}(a \mid s) \end{aligned} \quad (52)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \text{const} \cdot \mathbb{E}[G(\tau) \mid \tau \in \mathcal{T}_B]\nabla_{\theta}\pi_{\theta}(a \mid s) \\ &\quad + (\mathbb{E}[G(\tau) \mid \tau \in \mathcal{T}_G] - \mathbb{E}[G(\tau) \mid \tau \in \mathcal{T}_B]) P(\tau \in \mathcal{T}_G \mid \theta_{\text{old}}) \nabla_{\theta}\pi_{\theta}(a \mid s) \end{aligned} \quad (53)$$

Note the highlighted term in green ($P(\tau \in \mathcal{T}_G \mid \theta_{\text{old}})$) is the direction of the gradient ascent on parameter θ .

Justification of the assumptions.

- Regarding the non-zero probability of recovering the optimal policy at initialization, it is standard in theoretical analyses to assume a uniform distribution of a random variable at initialization (see [13]).
- In reference to the realizability condition implied by Assumption 3, the expressiveness of the policy class parameterized by θ is an underlying assumption for deep learning models, supported by the The Universal Approximation Theorem [17].

Observation. Since the goal of the learning agent is to maximize $P(\tau \in \mathcal{T}_G \mid \theta)$ (i.e., to converge the agent policy to the distribution of acceptable trajectories), we can see that the second term provides the target direction with rate $(\mathbb{E}[G(\tau) \mid \tau \in \mathcal{T}_G] - \mathbb{E}[G(\tau) \mid \tau \in \mathcal{T}_B])$. Therefore, the ascent rate will decrease when the cumulative rewards from unacceptable trajectories (i.e., the false positive rewards) gets higher. In addition, the first term $\text{const} \cdot \mathbb{E}[G(\tau) \mid \tau \in \mathcal{T}_B]\nabla_{\theta}\pi_{\theta}(a \mid s)$ can be regarded as the deviation term of target direction. This formalization follows the intuition that the presence of false positive rewards can slow down the convergence rate of the learning agent.

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